

Infra-red Spectra of Substituted 2-Thiohydantoin

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Infra-red spectra of 2-thiohydantoin, 3-N-phenyl-, 3-N-*o*-tolyl-, 3-N-*p*-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin, in KBr matrix and in dioxane, and of 3-methyl- and 3-ethyl-2-thiohydantoin in KBr matrix and methylene-chloride medium were recorded. The effect on absorption frequencies of these compounds in organic phase has been discussed.

Hydantoin and thiohydantoin have significant importance in medicinal chemistry. Considerable amount of work has been reported in the literature in connection with their activity-structure relationships¹⁻⁶. Infra-red spectral data have been utilized for this purpose and the characteristic absorption frequencies for substituted five-membered heterocyclic rings are critically discussed by various workers⁷⁻¹⁰. In our present work we are attempting to study the effect of solvent medium on the infra-red absorption frequencies of 2-thiohydantoin, 3-N-phenyl-, 3-N-*o*-tolyl-, 3-N-*p*-tolyl-, 3-methyl-, 3-ethyl-2-thiohydantoin. The existence of tautomeric forms in similar compounds has been reported in the literature.

EXPERIMENTAL

AnalaR quality reagents were used in the preparations of: (1) 2-thiohydantoin¹¹, (2) 3-N-phenyl-2-thiohydantoin¹², (3) 3-N-*o*-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin¹³, (4) 3-N-*p*-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin¹⁴, (5) 3-methyl-2-thiohydantoin¹⁵ and (6) 3-ethyl-2-thiohydantoin¹⁶. The compounds were purified by standard methods¹¹⁻¹⁶, checked for their purity (m.p., C, H, N and S analysis) and then used for the spectral analysis.

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The infra-red spectra of the compounds were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer-521, in KBr matrix and in dioxane for compounds 1 to 4 and in KBr matrix and in methylenechloride for compounds 5 and 6 (Figures 1 to 7).

DISCUSSION

On trying to isolate a few complexes of substituted 2-thiohydantoin with the metal ions of the first transition series in solid state, it was observed that the nature, colour and the structure of the resulting complexes depend upon the *pH* of the solution and the nature of the solvent media used. Potentiometric studies of the complex formation in solutions also showed some interesting phenomena¹⁷. Even a slight change in conditions lead to entirely different types of complexes. Hence compounds 1 and 3 were studied in dioxane and 5 and 6 in methylenechloride medium to study the possible existence of the tautomeric forms

Fig. 1. Infra-red spectra of 2-Thiohydantoin and 3-N-phenyl 2-thiohydantoin in KBr matrix.

Fig. 2. Infra-red spectra of 3-N-*o*-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin and 3-N-*p*-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin in KBr matrix.

Fig. 3. Infra-red spectra of 3-Methyl-2-thiohydantoin in KBr matrix.

Fig. 4. Infra-red spectra of 3-Ethyl-2-thiohydantoin in KBr matrix.

Fig. 5. Infra-red spectra of 2-Thiohydantoin and 3-N-o-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin in dioxane.

Fig. 6. Infra-red spectra of 3-Methyl-2-thiohydantoin in methylenechloride.

Fig. 7. Infra-red spectra of 3-Ethyl-2-thiohydantoin in methylenechloride.

of these reagents^{13,14,18}. Infra-red spectra of 2-thiohydantoin shows intense bands at 1700 cm^{-1} due to five membered lactam carbonyl. Similarly, C = S stretching¹⁹ in the same

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ring is indicated in the region 1400–1550, and 950–1050 cm^{-1} . No band is observed at 1600–1640 cm^{-1} which is the characteristic of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching frequency. Hence of the two possible structures for 2-thiohydantoin, constitution (I) may be reasonably assigned to this compound. Various other tautomeric forms have been suggested by different workers^{20–27} which were necessary to explain the nature and mode of the reactions under investigation.

(R = H, $-\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $-o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $-p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$)

The N–H proton in (I) is bound to be acidic as it is flanked on two sides by $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\text{C}=\text{S}$ groups. Such examples are well known in the literature^{28–31}. Weak bands in the region of 2550–2600 and 1600–1640 cm^{-1} in dioxane media may be assigned^{32,33} to $-\text{SH}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ respectively. In-plane and out-of-plane bending vibrations for primary amines are respectively, 1560–1640, and 650–900 cm^{-1} . In secondary amines a weak band at 1490–1580 cm^{-1} represents N–H bending³¹. The C–N stretching vibrations do not differ much in position from C–C stretching bands but are strong because of the greater polarity of the C–N linkage. In primary amines the asymmetric and symmetric N–H stretching are near 2.82μ and 2.92μ , and are rather strong. Secondary amines are normally expected to have only one band in this region, though there is a possibility of *cis* and *trans* forms with one band for each. The carbonyl stretching is observed to be between 1630–1700 cm^{-1} , N–H is absent, while the C–N deformation is at frequency 1290 cm^{-1} . Various bands in 3-N-phenyl-2-thiohydantoin^{34,35} may be assigned as : 1770–1740 cm^{-1} , ring $\text{C}=\text{O}$ vibration; 1600 cm^{-1} , phenyl group vibration; 1425–1405 cm^{-1} , $\text{C}=\text{S}$ vibration; 1530–1500 cm^{-1} , N–H vibration. Substitutions of *o*-tolyl and *p*-tolyl groups in the parent compound do not affect these bands

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as seen from the results. The band frequencies in these compounds for these groups are in the region of 1540–1575 cm^{-1} , and 1540–1670 cm^{-1} , respectively.

The spectral curves for 3-methyl- and 3-ethyl-2-thiohydantoin in KBr matrix could be compared with the data reported in the literature. Thus, when the carbonyl group was considered, we get, the characteristic frequency (sharp peak) at 1740–1745 cm^{-1} . The observation is in agreement with that of Ramchandran and Co-workers³⁴, who reported it to be 1770–1745 cm^{-1} . Replacement of oxygen by sulphur in the hydantoin series has been observed to cause a general shift of the absorption of the longer wave-lengths. Methylation of 2-thiohydantoin confirmed the production of derivatives of the thiol form $-\text{N} = \text{C}-(\text{SH})$ in contrast to the 2-oxo-compounds which form N-methyl products^{20,36}. Replacement of N-3 hydrogen atom with methyl group affects not only the infra-red frequencies but also known to affect the toxicity^{37,38}. It was thus inferred that the carbonyl stretching frequency shifts corresponding to a structural change is indicative of the related change in the electron distribution.

Clow³⁹ determined the diamagnetic susceptibilities of a series of thioureas and concluded that the structure tends to the extreme forms $(=\text{N}-)\text{C} = \text{S}$ as the degree of substitution on the nitrogen atom was increased. Careful study of the infra-red spectra of 3-methyl- and 3-ethyl-2-thiohydantoin, in organic medium, reveals that no significant bands are obtained which could conveniently be ascribed to $\text{C} = \text{N}$ and $\text{S}-\text{H}$ groups. A weak band at 2680 cm^{-1} for 3-ethyl- and 2684 cm^{-1} for 3-methyl-2-thiohydantoin signify a very little probability for $\text{C} = \text{N}$ grouping, while a band at 1620 cm^{-1} for 3-methyl-2-thiohydantoin signifies for $-\text{SH}$. Hence one may conclude that the tendency of the methyl and ethyl groups on N-3 atom to affect the intensity and the characteristic wavelengths of these compounds has greater masking effect under the present conditions. In KBr matrix no such weak peaks were observed which clearly indicates that these compounds could exist with structure (I) in solid state.

The methylene group of thiohydantoin show a significant peak at 2920 cm^{-1} which could be ascribed to in phase-stretching vibrations. Asymmetric methyl and methylene deformation occurs between 1412–1457 cm^{-1} , either weak or with medium intensities. The C-H symmetric deformation mode of methyl and methylene groups may be assigned to the region between 1309–1392 cm^{-1} . Various other bands in 3-methyl- and 3-ethyl-2-thiohydantoin may be assigned as follows: 3190 cm^{-1} , either of the two imino functions; 3020–3035 cm^{-1} , $-\text{CH}_2-$ out of phase stretching vibrations; 1740–1745 cm^{-1} , lactam ring carbonyl vibrations; 1530 cm^{-1} , $-\text{NH}-$ vibrations; 709–776 cm^{-1} , breathing vibrations of the ring.

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